

Respon Sprektrum

Lantai	Tinggi (m)	Elevasi (m)	Perpindahan (mm)		Perpindahan Elastik		Story Drift		Batas Drift (mm)
			X	Y	X	Y	X	Y	
Lt.1	6	11.95	2.5	4.579	1.43	2.89	5.23	10.60	90
Lt. Mezz	6	5.95	1.074	1.687	1.07	1.69	3.94	6.19	90
Lt. Dasar	1.45	-0.05	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	21.75
Turunan	6.5	-1.5	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	97.5

Time History Chi Chi Earthquake

Lantai	Tinggi (m)	Elevasi (m)	Perpindahan (mm)		Perpindahan Elastik		Story Drift		Batas Drift (mm)
			X	Y	X	Y	X	Y	
Lt.1	6	11.95	2.282	4.343	1.30	2.73	4.77	10.01	90
Lt. Mezz	6	5.95	0.982	1.614	0.98	1.61	3.60	5.92	90
Lt. Dasar	1.45	-0.05	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	21.75
Turunan	6.5	-1.5	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	97.5